

Cure-induced wrinkles and compression strength knock-down in uni-directional composites.

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Acknowledgement:

- Turbo: Towards tURbine Blade production with zero waste, Horizon Europe

Fatigue failure of wrinkles in load carrying laminates

Mendonça, H.G., Mikkelsen, L.P., Zhang, B., Allegri, G., Hallet, S.R., Fatigue Delaminations in Composites for Wind Turbine Blades with Artificial Wrinkle Defects, *Int. J. of Fatigue*, **170**, 107822, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2023.107822>, 2023.

The concept of cure-induced wrinkles

Wind turbine blade composite consists of fibres embedded in polymer "resin".

- The polymer will have to polymerise to give the blade its mechanical properties.
 - This process is referred to as **curing**.
 - Performed at elevated temperatures
- **Temperature gradients** occur during **heating** or **exothermal heat release** from the resin.
- The temperature gradients results in varying build-up of resin stiffness.
- This allows the fibres to buckle, driven by variations in thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage of the resin.
- This results in the phenomenon called ***"Cure-induced wrinkles"***.

Cure-induced Wrinkles

Jørgensen, J. K., Mikkelsen, L. P., and Maes, V. (2024). Finite element simulation of the driving mechanisms for cure-induced wrinkles. In *Proceedings of the 21st European Conference on Composite Materials - Special Sessions*, Binetruy, C. & Jacquemin, F. (eds.). European Society for Composite Materials, vol. 8, 31-36, 2-5 July, 2024, Nantes, France, <https://doi.org/10.60691/yj56-np80>.

Cure-induced Wrinkles

- Glass fibres
- Epoxy

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 Glass fibres

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Model for precise cure shrinkage predictions

Jørgensen, J. K., Maes, V. K., Mikkelsen, L. P., & Andersen, T. L., A Precise Prediction of the Chemical and Thermal Shrinkage during Curing of an Epoxy Resin. *Polymers*, 16(2435), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16172435>, 2024

Experimental measured and numerical predicted cure-induced shrinkage

Material characterizations of the resin system

- DSC measurements

- Chemical shrinkage

- Thermal contraction/expansion

Stiffness build-up during curing

$$E_m = \begin{cases} E_m^0, & X < X_\sigma \\ E_m^0 (1 - X_m) + X_m E_m^\infty, & X_\sigma \leq X < X_{\text{end}}, \text{ with} \\ E_m^\infty, & X \geq X_{\text{end}} \end{cases}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_m = E_m \varepsilon_m^{\text{mech}},$$

$$\Delta\sigma_f = E_f \varepsilon_f^{\text{mech}}.$$

$$X_m = \left(\frac{X - X_\sigma}{X_{\text{end}} - X_\sigma} \right).$$

$$E_{f,c}(X) = \left(0.01 + \frac{0.99}{1 + \exp(q(X - X_\sigma))} \right) E_f, \quad \varepsilon_f^{\text{mech}} < 0.$$

Jørgensen, J. K., Mikkelsen, L. P., Maes, V. K., Prediction of cure-induced wrinkles aimed at the manufacturing of largewind turbine blades. Submitted 2025.

Predict the cure-induced wrinkle formation

Final wrinkle shape

Compressive failure mechanism

Figure 15: Contour plot of additional fibre rotation at three different loading stages for the $T_{\text{pre-cure}} = 50^\circ\text{C}$.

Costa, S, Jørgensen, J. K., Mikkelsen, L. P., Effect of curing temperature on the longitudinal compressive strength of unidirectional composites. Under preparation 2025.

Compression strength knock-down

Costa, S, Jørgensen, J. K., Mikkelsen, L. P., Effect of curing temperature on the longitudinal compressive strength of unidirectional composites. Under preparation 2025.

Currently ignoring visco-elastic relaxation during curing

Mikkelsen, L.P., Jørgensen, J.K., Mortensen, U.A., Andersen, T.L., In-situ cure-induced strain measurements using optical fiber Bragg gratings for residual stress determinations in thermosets, *Solids*, 6(1), <https://doi.org/10.3390/solids6010003>, 2025.

Conclusion

- Demonstrate that curing under varying temperature may lead to cure-induced wrinkles
- Cure-induced wrinkles may reduce the compression strength significantly
- Small variations in the cure-conditions may lead to large strength reduction due to the present of cure-induced wrinkles